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Reviewing the Effect of Television Violence on Children's Behaviour and Development: The Role of Public Relations Officers

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ABSTRACT

This study reviewed the effect of television violence on children's behaviour and development: The role of public relations officers. use of television by children has been a source of debate and among scholars because of the preponderance of uncensored messages in some instances. To achieve the aims of the study, the researcher reviewed the following sub-headings: Children and Television Viewing Habit, Concept of Development Communication, Effect of Television on Children's Behaviour, Neurological Effect, the Mean World Syndrome, Aggression Effect and Desensitization Effect. Based on the review, the study conclude that television sets are commonly found in most homes. As such, access to the medium is prevalent among young people especially children. However, viewing violent contents on the television screen can be detrimental to their cognitive development due to their undiscerning minds. Hence, the implications of this chapter establish that exposure to viewing violent contents on television has negative influence on the children's behavioural outcomes. Therefore, the study recommends that: Parents and adults should be active in monitoring and scrutinizing the type of television contents and programmes viewed by children. adult programmes which have violent contents should not be aired on television until sometime beyond 9 pm. when the children would have been expected to sleep.

Key Words: effect, television violence, children's behavior, development

INTRODUCTION

Television is an important medium for most people, young or old. It is considered to be a potentially strong agent for children, adolescents and other family members, especially with its combined effects of audio and visual elements. Through advancement in technology, television can be accessed easily via cables or satellite. This has provided audience with variety of messages which communicate different human activities. Kamaruzaman (2019) states, that with various programmes, television has caught the attention of most people. Compared to other media, television seems to be one of the most favourable and accessible media to some people, including children.

Burton (2013) argues that the use of television by children has been a source of debate and among scholars because of the preponderance of uncensored messages in some instances. Chinemere and Adekanye (2014) states that "Television is a compact structure that creates an intimate mediurti; it brings the world into our homes and brings its audience into direct relationship with particular values and attitudes". Rodmañ (2016) notes that television remains the most time consuming activity, yet the main source of news and information. Roberts, Foehr and Rideout (2015) carried out a national study that took an in-depth look at the television viewing habits of children and adolescents in the United States of America. Surveying 2,200 children and adolescents from eight to 18 years of age, it was

shown that, on average, children spent 6 hours a day with the television but spent only 2 hours a day with parents and just 50 minutes a day on homework. It was further noted that despite all the newly developed technologies that are available adolescents spent the most time (nearly four hours a day) watching T.V, including live and pre-recorded T.V, DVDs and videos.

Similarly, in a research conducted in Nigeria by Usaini (2020) on the “influence of television on the social behaviour among teenagers”, it was seen that teenagers spent more time watching television. About 68.8% of the respondents said they spend several hours watching television. The teenagers stated that they spent their time exploring television programmes/contents, such as movies, soap operas, reality TV shows, music videos, fashion shows and entertainment news. Television is the medium through which political messages and entertainment are transmitted to the various audience segments. It is a significant medium for transmitting information to the audience.

Behavioural problems can occur in children of all ages. Some children are given to serious behavioural problems such as physical fights, drug abuse, aggression etc. Rutter and Taylor (2022) observe that: Behavioural problems occur when the child continues to behave badly for several months or longer and such behaviours break the rules accepted in his/her family and community. These behavioural problems may be disruptive, delinquent and deviant. Also, they opined that these sorts of behavioural problems can affect a child’s development and also interfere with his ability to live a normal life.

Roza and Michael (2021) argue that violence by young people is one of the most visible forms of behavioural problems in human society. This connotes that concern about television and children behaviour is on the increase, not only because of television’s popularity but as a result of its effects on children’s behaviour. Children are exposed to different social environments, hence, they react differently to television messages. A typical African child has different social environment from that of the child in the West (Gbadeyan, 2018).

Researchers such as Kadiri and Muhammed (2021) conclude that culture and the media are some of the factors that affect the way teenagers dress, talk, walk or even the type of music or food they want. The media are believed to cause intended and unintended changes in people’s behaviour. They also reinforce what has already existed or prevent a change to what has existed (McQuail, 2014). As television competes with other activities and experiences in a child’s life, the child’s attitudes and beliefs about television and about life in general are important determinants of his or her response to television. Television may be a socializing force but it intervenes in complex ways with other forces in a child’s life to determine the patterns of socialization for that child (Kadiri & Muhammed, 2021).

Much of television’s power and influence over adults and children lies in its capacity to strike deep emotional chords in viewers and to increase their identifications with characters to arouse emotional responses and in general to deepen their involvement in the television experience. UNESCO surveyed children in 23 countries around the world in 1998 and it was discovered that 91 percent of them had access to television sets in their homes and not just in the U.S. Canada, Europe, but also in the Arab states, Latin America, Asia and Africa. More than half (51%) of boys living in war zones and high-crime areas chose action heroes as role models ahead of any other images; and a remarkable 88 percent of the children surveyed could identify the Arnold Schwarzenegger character from the film Terminator. UNESCO (2008) reports that the Terminator “seems to represent the characteristics that children think are necessary to cope with difficult situations”.

In recent times, increased attention has been focused by many professionals on television (Gerbner, 2018; Kadiri and Muhammed, 2021) with regard to its impact on human lives at any stage of development. According to Healy (2014), the impact of television is more on children because they are more impressionable and vulnerable than adults. Childhood is a period during which children feel the pressure of constructing an adult identity. Thus, television can have a profound impact on children as well as on adolescent’s development and behaviour. Television is now a household medium across Nigeria with increasing accessibility and limited censorship by the society.

Children and Television Viewing Habit

Studies have shown that children are among the heaviest users of television (Adam, 2014). Gortmaker (2021) defines television habit as the average viewing time individuals give to the television set. He adds that television viewing patterns may impact positively or negatively on an individual’s cognitive

development. Viewing television programmes for one to two hours daily, on the average, may enhance an individual's cognitive skill development, while a habit of three hours or more of television viewing of general audience programmes may reduce the time an individual would spend engaging verbally and socially with family members and significant others, which is a prerequisite for effective cognitive skill development.

The mass media play a significant role in people's lives and affect family routines, social interactions, cultural norms, and leisure activities - all of which impact upon contemporary childhood. Television is particularly significant in early childhood; it is the child's first and most enduring contact with the mass media and an integral part of the overall environment in which early childhood development occurs (Victoria, 2019). The amount of television children watch varies immensely. Viewing habits range from the child who does not watch television at all, to the child who sits in front of television set nearly all waking hours. The decision to watch television is influenced by several factors, including the lack of any preferred or required alternative activity; fondness for particular programmes or characters; habit; and mood. The longer a child has spent time watching television at any one time, the more difficult he or she is to distract. This means that during the formative years, children spend more time in front of a television set.

As it is today, television has become a major influence educationally, as well as on social learning. With most families owning at least, one television set, children have become television-friendly from at least, the age of six. It is found in many homes and it requires a minimal skill to operate, such that children find it easy to manipulate its visual nature; their viewing appetite increases from the age of eight into early adolescence with viewing averaging four hours a day. Television has become the dominant medium to which the children are exposed, obviously for children and of course everybody. Children are the most captivated of television audience, since childhood is a period of seeking, gathering and learning from information so gathered. According to Sanders (2014), the "average child," between the ages of six and eighteen, will have spent 4,000 hours listening to radio and CD5, watching 16,000 hours of television, and several thousands more hours of movies. This position is further supported in a survey by Certain and Kahn (2022) which states that the percentage of hours young children who watch television is related to several variables, which include early television viewing and maternal education.

Their longitudinal study indicates that greater television viewing in early childhood is associated with greater viewing at school age due to environmental influence, child preferences or habit, or the interaction of both, and less educated mothers. The interconnection between early childhood development and television begins at the start of life. Those who watch more than three hours per day are more likely to have behavioural problems such as stealing or fighting than those who watch television for less than an hour per day, making exposure to television one of the most enduring, powerful and consistent experiences of childhood.

Concept of Development Communication

According to UNICEF (2021), development communication is a two-way process for sharing ideas and knowledge using a range of communication tools and approaches that empower individuals and communities to take actions to improve their lives. The Thusong Government Center (2022) describes it as "providing people with information they can use in bettering their lives, which aims at making public programmes and policies real, meaningful and sustainable". Communication and development have been viewed as closely intertwined phenomena, where one is believed to guarantee the other (Sosale, 2022). Development communication or communication for development involves understanding people, their beliefs and values, the social and cultural norms that shape their lives (Srampickal, 2016). Sosale (2022) further notes that, development communication involves engaging people as they identify problems, propose solutions and act upon them. It is a two-way process for sharing ideas and knowledge using a range of communication tools and approaches that empower Individuals to take actions to improve their lives. Similarly, Servaes, (2022) has posited that:

All those involved in the analysis and application of communication for development - or what can broadly be termed "development communication" - would probably agree that in essence

development communication is the sharing of knowledge aimed at reaching a consensus for action that takes into account the interests, needs and capacities of all concerned.

The central element in development communication is sharing of knowledge. Sharing knowledge can be in the areas of health, agriculture, science, environment, education, empowerment, sanitation and hygiene etc. In the case of television and its influence on children's behaviour, there is no doubt that television as a medium of communication plays a vital role in the socialization process of children. Some proponents of this view argue that television is an early window. In this context, television is a medium with the greatest potential for transmitting information and beliefs from one group of persons to another. It is influential in the socialization of children.

Effect of Television on Children's Behaviour

Television has the potential to generate both positive and negative effects, but many researches seem to have paid more attention to the negative effects than the positive ones, particularly, the behaviour of children and adolescents. The focus here is on the negative effects. Several negative effects on children's behaviour have been attributed to viewing certain television programmes that portray contents that are adverse on the habit formation of children.

Neurological Effect

This refers to the effect television has on nervous system, especially regarding structure, functions, and abnormalities. Research indicates that most parts of the brain, including parts responsible for logical thought, tune out during television viewing and produce brainwaves in the low alpha range. Some scientists believe that the release of high amounts of dopamine reduces the amount of the neurotransmitter available for control of movement, perception of pain and pleasure and formation of feelings, especially when a person spends much time sitting in front of television. According to David (2014), while alpha waves achieved through meditation are beneficial, too much time spent in low alpha wave state caused by television can cause unfocused day dreaming and inability to concentrate. This connotes that prolonged exposure to rapid image changes (like on a TV show designed for an infant) during critical periods of brain development, may precondition the mind to expect high levels of stimulation. However, cultivation theory hypothesizes that people who are heavy viewers of television will be more likely to hold beliefs and attitudes congruent with the messages and world view of television. This may then make the pace of real life less able to sustain children's attention. The more hours a child views rapid-fire television, the more likely he will have attention challenges later in life (Swanson, 2022).

Too much of watching television can actually cause harmful changes to a child's brain structure. Television viewing is directly or indirectly associated with neuro-cognitive development of the children. Some neuro-anatomists argue that excessive television viewing (more than five hours per day, seven days per week) can have a serious toll on a child's cognition. The limbic system of the brain (the emotional part) is designated as the image-making centre. It is believed that the limbic system develops more slowly when young persons spend half of their life in front of the television set. A strong limbic system provides a natural defence against the constant violent images that penetrate consumer culture. Violence on television could lead, to anxiety. Healy (2014) explains that another need that the media fill for children is one of entertainment. This could happen due to the power of environmental experiences in shaping the developing brain because of the flexibility of its neuronal connectivity. Repeated exposure to any stimulus in a child's environment may forcibly impact mental and emotional growth by either setting up particular circuitry ("habits of mind") or depriving the brain of other experiences. Valkenburg (2021) argues that:

The anxiety hypothesis assumes that the television- induced fright leads to regression in behaviour, which is expressed in a reduction in the quantity of imaginative play. These television images have an effect on children's imagination. Nowadays children do not have to engage their imagination. They do not need to make up new stories or invent games.

The statement above focuses on the amount of time children watch television. The consensus is that too much time and exposure of children to television can create a possibility of contents of television programmes affecting the child's cognitive development if the child continues to glue to television programmes. Studies of Johnson, Cohen, Kasen and Brook (2014) and that of Zimmerman and

Christakis (2017) have shown that content is a crucial part of television. There is a chemical change in the brain, similar to that which is seen in post-traumatic stress disorder when a child spends too much time watching television.

The Mean World Syndrome

“Mean world syndrome” is a term coined by George Gerbner (2012) to describe a phenomenon whereby violence-related television makes viewers believe that the world is more dangerous than it actually is. Gerbner, a pioneer researcher on the effects of television on society, argues that people who watch a large amount of television tend to think of the world as an intimidating and unforgiving place. This connotes that there is a direct correlation between the amount of television one watches and the amount of fear one harbours about the world. The direction of causality remains debatable due to the fact that some persons who are scared of the world would more likely retreat from it and in turn spend more time indoors, engaging in solitary activity such as television watching. As such, viewing violence on television can increase the fear of becoming a victim because it instills fear on its viewers to see the world as a dangerous place. Nabi and Sullivan (2021) observe that:

The amount of television viewing directly influenced prevalence estimates of violence in society, as well as intentions to take protective measures, and indirectly affected mean world attitude. The number of opinions, images, and attitudes that viewers tend to form when watching television will have a direct influence on how the viewer perceives the real world. They will reflect and refer to the most common images or recurrent messages thought to have an impact on their own real lives.

Television viewing colours our experiences and makes us less trusting of others. For example, a child, after viewing some violent situations on television might think that the real world is cruel because young children have trouble distinguishing reality from fantasy. This means that children who watch more of violent television contents may tend to believe that the ‘world of television is the real world and it is a “mean world”, where people do not trust one another. Television can fill one’s mind with negativity, bombard one with image manipulation via commercials and give one a distorted view of reality by showing one everything that is bad about the world.

Aggression Effect

One of the most worrisome behaviours that parents are faced with is the tendency of their children to perform acts of aggression. Often, there is a correlation between exhibited acts of aggression among children and what is displayed on the television screen. Many television shows tend to depict aggressive behaviours such as hitting, raping or even killing. According to Bushman and Huesmann (2021), one of the reasons the effects of television violence may be so powerful is that aggression and television violence feed off each other. This reciprocal relationship between television violence and aggression can create a vicious circle. The struggle between the hero and the shadow pervades many children’s programmes (Kolter & Calvert, 2013). Many viewers, especially children, like the fast action and use of weaponry common in many violent scenes. Often, violence is what makes the hero of a story. Children admire the hero and often want to identify with him. If the hero of the story uses violence to gain victory, then children will learn that violence is needed to overcome the enemy and be victorious.

Children most at risk of forming aggressive behaviour when they become young adults are those who watch a steady amount of television violence, perceive it as realistic, and identify with the aggressor (Bushman & Huesmann, 2001). The combination of extensive exposure to violence and identification with aggressive characters is a particularly potent predictor of subsequent aggression for many children (Huesmann et al., 2013). Hence, children who initially are high in aggression respond to aggressive television programmes with higher levels of aggression than they would under neutral conditions.

Desensitization Effect

Desensitisation is a word used to describe the ways in which watching acts of violence reduces viewers’ responsiveness (Bushman & Huesmann, 2016). Cantor (2022) explains that desensitization occurs when an emotional response is repeatedly evoked, and the action tendency that is associated with the emotion proves irrelevant or unnecessary. According to Gunter and McAleer (2017), children who watch a violent programme sequence tend to take longer to give a warning about the violence or misbehaviour of other children when compared to similar children who have not watched any

television violence. This gives credence to the tenets of the cultivation theory as Gerbner (2017) posits that viewers of television tend to cultivate new attitudes that seem to be normal compared to what is expected of them in the society. Such attitudes are often exhibited by younger ones irrespective of whether they are accepted in the society or not. Gerbner maintains that people who spend more time living in the television world tend to be susceptible to believing what they see in the television world as real.

Children are very impressionable and are easily desensitized to the violence they watch on television. For instance, research by Kadiri and Muhammed (2021) has shown that young children are aroused by aggressive scenes on television and as a result, show higher levels of emotion than when they watch passive programmes. The arousal diminishes with repeated exposure to television and the violence no longer affects them. When people are no longer aroused by violence they become less responsive to human suffering and may not be quick to help or may not intervene during an emergency. When there is a problem, arousal levels are high which can result to an aggressive response. The promotion of violent behaviour leads to the belief that violence is common and acceptable. According to Suler (2015), this reduces normal inhibitions about behaving in certain anti-social ways, and may lead to inability to exert conscious control over human behaviour. Similarly, Tabet (2020) argues that children who watch a model rewarded for performing violently in the media are more likely to experience a desensitization effect and behave in a similar manner. When continually watching violence, children can become desensitized to pain and suffering of others.

According to Huesmann, Moise, Podolski and Eron (2013), there are stronger desensitisation effects for males than there are for females. They suggest that boys who watch excessive amounts of television violence will show lower than average physiological arousal in response to scenes of violence. This depicts the fact that frequent watching of violent contents on television may cause children to be less anxious about violence but see it as mere 'normal'. Browne and Hamilton (2015) argue that there is consistent evidence that violent imagery on television, film or computer game has substantial short-term effect on arousal, thoughts, and emotions. This increases the likelihood of aggressive or fearful behaviour in children.

PR officers, whether in house or based with an agency, are likely to work with other communications professionals, such as marketing teams, designers and copywriters. Public relations officers (also known as public relations account executives) plan and develop PR strategies for brands, individuals and organisations. As part of this, they will identify target audiences, then develop and share information that's tailored to audience preferences. Some PR officers handle crisis communications, dealing with negative information about a client and aiming to protect their reputation.

Some PR officers work in house and focus on projects and campaigns for their own employer, while others are employed by agencies (or are freelance) and work with a number of clients. PR is considered part of the 'marketing mix' – all of the activities a brand needs to do to promote their services or products. PR officers, whether in house or based with an agency, are likely to work with other communications professionals, such as marketing teams, designers and copywriters.

Typical duties include:

1. Planning publicity strategies and campaigns.
2. Writing and producing presentations, articles, press releases and social media posts.
3. Designing or project managing the production of visual communications and digital content.
4. Dealing with enquiries from the public, the press and related organisations.
5. Organising and attending promotional events such as press conferences, open days, exhibitions, tours and visits.
6. Speaking publicly at interviews, press conferences and presentations.
7. Providing clients/colleagues with information about new promotional opportunities and current PR campaigns' progress.
8. Analysing media coverage.
9. Commissioning or undertaking relevant market research and data analysis.
10. Coordinating and analysing the success of online advertising.

Keeping records of progress, budgets and timescales, and keeping clients/colleagues up to date with these. Working hours could be irregular when deadlines are approaching or if you're involved in events. You may also need to be on call (available to respond to emergencies outside working hours) at times – for example, if a client needs urgent advice to handle negative publicity.

Theoretical Framework

This discourse is anchored on the cultivation theory of the mass media. The cultivation theory is a social theory which examines the long-term effects of television. It was propounded by George Gerbner in 1976 after conducting several large research projects on the effects of television on viewers. He compared television's socializing force to that of religion, claiming that television defines social roles; standardizes behaviour and homogenizes communities much as religion did in early human history. Also, because television portrays excessive amounts of violence, it can cause people to develop Mean World Syndrome, or the idea that the world is scarier than it really is. Gerbner sorted television's effects into two categories: first order and second order. First order effects refer to general beliefs about the world, while second order effects involve specific attitudes towards one's environment or certain aspects of society, like law enforcement. Shanahan (2018) asserts that cultivation is a method for gauging the impact of television viewing on beliefs, behaviours, and attitudes.

Riddle (2019) corroborates that the primary proposition of cultivation theory is that "the more time people spend 'living' in the television world, the more likely they are to believe social reality portrayed on television". Cultivation leaves people with a misperception of what is true in our world. This means that high frequency viewers of television are more susceptible to television messages and the belief that they are real and valid. Heavy viewers are exposed to more violence and therefore are affected by the Mean World Syndrome. Cultivation theorists hold that television viewing can have long-term effects that gradually affect the audience. Their primary focus falls on the effects of viewing on the attitudes of the viewer as opposed to created behaviour. Heavy viewers of television are thought to be 'cultivating' attitudes that seem to believe that the world created by television is an accurate depiction of the real world.

The theory suggests that prolonged watching of television can tend to induce a certain paradigm about violence in the world. The theory denotes that this cultivation of attitudes is based on attitudes already present in our society and that the media take those attitudes which are already present and re-present them bundled in a different packaging to their audiences. One of the main tenets of the theory is that the media cultivate the status quo; they do not challenge it. Many times, viewers are unaware of the extent to which they absorb media and view themselves as moderate viewers when, in fact, they are heavy viewers. The theory suggests that the media possess a small but significant influence on the attitudes and beliefs of society about society. Those who absorb media contents are those who are more influenced.

However, the cultivation theory is similar to other media effects theories in the fundamental assumption that media contents influence behaviours on the audience. The theory, to an extent focuses on the long-term process of audience attitudes, while other media effects theories focus on immediate or short term behaviours of the mass audience.

CONCLUSION

Television sets are commonly found in most homes. As such, access to the medium is prevalent among young people especially children. However, viewing violent contents on the television screen can be detrimental to their cognitive development due to their undiscerning minds. Hence, the implications of this chapter establish that exposure to viewing violent contents on television has negative influence on the children's behavioural outcomes.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The following have been recommended:

1. Parents and adults should be active in monitoring and scrutinizing the type of television contents and programmes viewed by children.

2. The Censorship Board should be more alert to its duties so that television programmes for children that have inbuilt violent contents can be censored before they are aired.
3. Adult programmes which have violent contents should not be aired on television until sometime beyond 9 pm. when the children would have been expected to sleep.

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